

Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center

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**Comparison of operational ocean
forecasting systems**

by

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REPORT

***Project at the Mohn-Sverdrup Center,
department of the Nansen Environmental and
Remote Sensing Center***

Soazig Parouty

Introduction

I spent my third and last year of Engineering School in Bergen, where I followed courses at the Geophysical Institute. During the first semester the Mohn Sverdrup Center (part of the Nansen Center directed by Ola M. Johannessen) advertised some projects for Master Students that I applied for. So I had the opportunity to work from the 17th of January to the 15th of July 2005 in the numerical modelling and data assimilation group of the Nansen Center with Laurent Bertino as a supervisor. During the first four months I was still busy with some courses from the University of Bergen which were of interest (Remote Sensing, Field Course in Oceanography, Operational Oceanography and learning Norwegian as a foreign language), but could had a full time work during the last two months. The main purpose of my project was to compare different models of oceanographic forecasting, and compare the Norwegian forecasting system named TOPAZ with ARGO data.

I Presentation of the Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center

(from <http://www.nersc.no/index2.php>)

Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center (NERSC) is an independent non-profit research institute affiliated with the University of Bergen, Norway. The Nansen Center conducts basic and applied environmental research funded by national and international governmental agencies, research councils and industry.

Its vision is to make a significant contribution to the understanding, monitoring and forecasting of the world's environment and climate on regional and global scales. This is done through coordination and participation in national and international research programs focusing on:

- Studies of global and regional climate processes using numerical models together with observations from earth-monitoring satellites and field experiments.
- Modeling of the global and regional marine ecosystem and carbon cycle combined with use of satellite ocean color observations.
- Studies of ocean disposal of the greenhouse gas CO₂ as an option for reducing the rapid increase in atmospheric CO₂ concentration.
- Studies of coastal zone processes and ecosystem dynamics by integrated use of high resolution ocean circulation models and observations through advanced data assimilation systems.
- Studies of sea ice processes using coupled numerical models and observations from satellite.
- Operational monitoring and forecasting of the coastal zone as a tool for management and risk assessment.
- Operational monitoring and forecasting of ice conditions as a service to offshore industry, ship traffic and fishing industry.

NERSC's research strategy is to integrate the use of remote sensing and field observations with numerical modeling through the use of advanced data assimilation techniques.

The center teaches university courses and hosts graduate students and postdoctoral fellows from several nations. In 2005 the Nansen Group hosts 10 PhD candidates in Bergen and ? PhD candidates in St. Petersburg. Cooperation in research and education are established with several universities worldwide. Faculty members at the University of Bergen and senior staff at the Nansen Center hold adjunct

positions at the two institutions.

Research products developed at NERSC are commercialized through the company Terra Orbit A/S.

The Nansen Center in Bergen is organized in 5 scientific units which are Special Projects, Mohn-Sverdrup Center for Global Ocean Studies and Operational Oceanography, Coastal and Ocean Remote Sensing, Polar and Environmental Remote Sensing and G.C. Rieber Climate Institute.

The Nansen Center activities are a part of the Nansen Group which consists of

- Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center (established in 1986), Bergen, Norway
- TerraOrbit A/S (established in 1987), Bergen, Norway
- COTO Ltd (established in 1996), Bergen, Norway
- Nansen International Environmental and Remote Sensing Center (NIERSC), (established in 1992) St.Petersburg, Russia
- Nansen Environmental Research Centre India Pvt. Ltd. (NERCI) (established in 1998), Kochi, Kerala, India
- ARCTICA, Bergen, Norway (established in 1996)

The Nansen Group long-term strategy includes the establishment of similar centers in China, South America and Africa to provide an impetus for globally-oriented research in support of sustainable development of the earth's resources and to mitigate the adverse effects of climate change.

Prof. Ola M. Johannessen, the founder-director of the group, is a Norwegian scientist and professor of international repute with over 30 years experience in the fields of oceanography, remote sensing, polar sciences and climate studies.

The group is inspired by the life of Fridtjof Nansen (1861-1930), renowned Norwegian biologist, oceanographer, polar explorer, diplomat and humanist. The FRAM expedition, conceived and led by Nansen to chart Arctic waters by freezing a ship into the pack ice and allowing it to drift for 3 years was completed in 1896. This laid the foundation for research in the Arctic Ocean, which is today known to be a key component of the global climate system. Nansen was empowered by 52 nations to issue the Nansen Passport to millions of war prisoners and refugees in the aftermath of the First World War and the Russian Revolution and organized their feeding and repatriation. In 1922, Nansen was awarded the Nobel Peace Prize for his humanitarian work. He played a key role in Norway's separation from Sweden in 1905 and also served as Norway's representative to Great Britain and to the League of Nations.

II Presentation of my project

1. First part: work on the Gulf of Mexico - comparisons between Mercator and Topaz.

To get used to some tools and files, I first looked at a few forecasts of NERSC and MERCATOR and tried to identify the differences between them. Then, I had to compare a MERCATOR and NERSC forecast during August 2004, in the Gulf of Mexico. I mainly had to make plots out of NetCDF files (network Common Data Form) and compare them. Having some matlab programs to look at made it easier to understand how these NetCDF files can be used. It is actually a very practical file format, from which relevant information can easily be picked out.

A PhD student working on the Gulf of Mexico explained me which kind of currents and eddies take place in the Gulf. Warm and saline water comes in the Gulf of Mexico through the Yucatan Strait, and forms a very strong current known as “Loop Current” which spreads inside the Gulf. After flowing out of the Gulf through the Florida Strait, this water becomes the Gulf Stream. What is a key thing to forecast in the Gulf of Mexico is how this strong current behaves: how far it goes, if any eddy will get separated from the main warm eddy... Indeed, there are some oil platforms on the northern part of the Gulf, and so a need to forecast strong currents in this area. What we tried to do was to find a way to characterize the front of this “Loop Current” (see Annex 1) in both MERCATOR and NERSC models and see which of these models was the most precise.

1.a Isotherms

First, I had to see if some specific isotherms at 200m deep could describe the front. This depth was chosen because it deep enough to avoid seeing too many small eddies or surface disturbances. Several plots were made for temperatures from 17 to 23°C (See Fig 01). Then, a temperature value corresponding to the isotherm which best described the Loop Current was chosen for each model. This temperature value wasn't the same for both of them since the surface water in MERCATOR is slightly colder and more salty than the water in NERSC (see Fig 03, 04, 05 and 06). It tends to be the other way round for deep water.

Fig 01: Isotherms at 200m deep
Left: MERCATOR from 17 to 21°C
Right: NERSC from 20 to 23°C

These selected isotherms were superposed on sea surface height observation (see Fig 03) made on the same day.

Fig 02: Background CLS, mainly showing the Loop Current
 Black line: MERCATOR, isotherm 18°C, 200m deep
 Blue line: NERSC, isotherm 21°C, 200m deep

However, having only figures at a specific depth is not enough to describe the whole eddy and to assess how good a model is. It is only useful to locate a water mass at this given depth. So the next step was to plot cross-sections out of the same NetCDF files. It would help seeing how deep the warm water mass goes in the two models. The models grids have latitude lines every 0.25°, and 25°N was chosen since this section was in the middle of the Loop Current on the 18th of August. Another section was studied, which corresponds to the Yucatan Strait at 22°N. For both of these sections, salinity, temperature and northward velocity were plotted, a special care was given on the scales. It had to be the same color scale for both models plots to make comparisons possible.

1.b Section at 25°N

Fig 03: MERC: temperature section plot at 25°N
 Minimum: 6,03°C
 Maximum: 30,19°C

Fig 04: NERSC: temperature section plot at 25°N.
 Minimum: 5,11°C
 Maximum: 30,95°C

According to NERSC prediction, the eddy is deeper and some structures appear to the west of the Loop Current due to a small eddy at 92°W (see Fig 02). Cherubin et al. (2005, [6]) have shown that a sinking of the Loop Current deepest active layer occurs before an eddy shedding event and is connected with

growth of the neighboring cyclones. That mechanism is clearly represented in the NERSC model (Fig 04).

Fig 05: MERCATOR: salinity at 25°N
Minimum: 34,95 psu
Maximum: 36,46 psu

Fig 06: NERSC: salinity at 25°N
Minimum: 34,98 psu
Maximum: 36,34 psu

These cross sections were also compared with the climatology (GDEM data). This showed that the water in the NERSC model is too fresh close to the surface, and MERCATOR fits a bit more to climatology.

From salinity and temperature section plot, we can notice that both models are too diffusive in the vertical dimension.

Fig 07 MERC northward velocity section at 25°N
Minimum: -0,71 m/s
Maximum: 1,07 m/s

Fig 08: NERSC northward velocity section at 25°N
Minimum value: -1,26 m/s
Maximum value: 1,33 m/s

I.c Yucatan Strait, 22°N

It is through the Yucatan Strait that the water is flowing inside the Gulf of Mexico.

Fig 09: MERCATOR, temperature
Minimum: 4,09°C
Maximum: 30,21°C

Fig 10: NERSC, temperature section
Minimum: 3,66°C
Maximum: 29,33°C

Fig 11: MERCATOR, salinity section
Minimum: 34,95 psu
Maximum: 36,47 psu

Fig 12: NERSC, salinity section
Minimum value: 34,98 psu
Maximum value: 36,38 psu

Comparisons with measurements showed that both models were accurate for temperature and salinity, with the tilt of the thermocline and the isohaline better represented in the NERSC model. Both models accurately locate the Antarctic intermediate deep water and the North Atlantic deep water.

The vertical interpolation of the model(s) onto a standard grid does not allow a detailed interpretation of the sections. Many features are lost in the interpolation. However the vertical interpolation does not introduce biases and respects the vertical position of water masses and the slope of the density lines.

Fig 13: MERCATOR, northward velocity
Minimum: -0,44 m/s
Maximum: 1,44 m/s

Fig 14: NERSC, northward velocity
Minimum: -0,44 m/s
Maximum: 1,17 m/s

The inflow and outflow through the Yucatan Strait differ from one model to the other. The fastest outflow is close to the surface and on the eastern part of the section with MERCATOR (Fig 23), whereas it extends more to the east with NERSC (Fig 24). For the inflow, MERCATOR has higher velocities within a smaller area close to the surface in the western part of the section (behaving like a intense coastal jet). What remains to be seen is whether the two models have the same salinity and temperature exchange through the Yucatan or not.

These two figures can be related to [2]. When the Loop Current front is growing northward, the upper inflow in the Yucatan strait is closer to the west coast and reaches a depth of 200m with a maximum speed of 1,20 m/s. At the same time, a southward current flows on the eastern part of the Yucatan strait, to a depth of 400 m deep and with a lower speed of 0,25 m/s. This situation is the one simulated by MERCATOR in Fig 14, and indeed, the eddy according to MERCATOR forecast is still attached (Fig 01 and 02). Then, according to [2], when the eddy has reached its highest latitude, and has been separated, the current in the Yucatan strait can slow down to 0,40 m/s, and spread eastward, remaining at the same depth. The southward outflow is also slower, it moves eastward and remains at 800 m depth. This is more or less the description of the NERSC simulation, while the eddy is no longer attached (see Fig 01 and Fig 02).

1.d Characterization of strong velocity gradient

The last task of my work on the Gulf of Mexico was to find a relevant parameter to locate the strong velocity gradient related to the front. Velocity gradient is a difficult variable to handle since it is noisy and not uniform. The selected isotherm at 200m deep and a given sea surface temperature (24cm) level line were superposed to a surface velocity gradient color map for both of the models. It turned out that, on the day chosen for this study, the isotherm was a slightly better parameter to determine the boundary of the Loop Current.

Fig 15: Inter-variable front comparison, MERCATOR
 Background: velocity gradient at the surface.
 Lines: SSH 24 cm in green; 18°C isotherm at 200m depth in black

Fig 16: Inter-variable front comparison, NERSC
 Background: velocity gradient at the surface.
 Lines: SSH 24 cm in green; 20°C isotherm at 200m depth in black

2. Second Part: Using ARGO data in model validation

During the second part of my project I used the ARGO data to compute differences between data and model forecasts. After a few information on the ARGO project and the importance of model validation, the task in itself and the results will be presented.

2.a The ARGO Project (from <http://www.argo.ucsd.edu/>)

Argo provides a new source of data from the top 2 km of the ocean. It uses a fleet of robotic floats that spend most of their life at specified depth and that go up to the surface regularly to make temperature and salinity profile measurements.

The plan is to launch 3,000 free-drifting profiling floats which will allow, for the first time, continuous monitoring of the temperature, salinity, and velocity of the upper ocean, with all data being relayed and made publicly available within hours after collection. Because over 90% of the increase in heat content of the air/land/sea climate system over the past 50 years occurred in the ocean [Levitus et al., 2001], Argo will effectively monitor the pulse of the global heat balance. It will improve our understanding of the ocean's role in climate, as well as spawning an enormous range of valuable ocean applications.

Argo deployments began in 2000 and in mid 2004 the array was over 40% complete. Today's tally of floats is shown in Fig 17

Fig 17: *Picture of the Argo array.*

Argo has several objectives. It will provide a quantitative description of the changing state of the upper ocean and the patterns of ocean climate variability from months to decades, including heat and freshwater storage and transport. The data will complement the Jason altimeter with measurements of subsurface temperature and salinity vertical structures and velocity information, with sufficient coverage and resolution to allow interpretations of altimetric sea surface height variability. Argo data will be used to initialize ocean and coupled ocean-atmosphere forecast models. A main focus of Argo is to document seasonal or decadal climate variability and to help us understand its predictability.

Argo is an international effort collecting high-quality temperature and salinity profiles from the upper 2000 m of the ice-free global ocean and currents at intermediate depths. Data come from battery-powered autonomous floats that spend most of their life drifting at depth where they are stabilized at a constant pressure level by being less compressible than sea water. At typically 10-day intervals, the floats pump fluid into an external bladder and rise to the surface over about 6 hours while measuring temperature and salinity. When at the surface, the floats transmit their position and data to satellites. The bladder then deflates and the float returns to its original density and sinks to drift until the cycle is repeated. Floats are designed to make about 150 such cycles.

Fig 18: Floats Cycle

Profiling floats were developed during the 1990-1998 World Ocean Circulation Experiment (WOCE), but despite their extensive earlier use, the technological challenges of building and maintaining the 3000-float Argo array should not be underestimated. Over 800 deployments will be required each year, and each float must deliver high-quality data while cycling over 200 atmospheres and through a temperature range that may approach 30°C. Argo continues to improve float performance and reliability through close collaboration between float operators and manufacturers.

All Argo data are publicly available in near real-time via the Global Telecommunications System GTS, and in scientifically quality-controlled form with a few months delay. Global coverage at the target 3° x 3° density should be achieved around 2006.

The design of the Argo network is based on experience from the present observing system, on recent knowledge of variability from the TOPEX/Poseidon altimeter, and on the requirements for climate and high-resolution ocean models.

The final array of 3000 floats will provide 100,000 T/S profiles and velocity measurements per year distributed over the global oceans at an average 3-degree spacing.

2.b Model validation

ARGO data can help validating a model. Nowadays, there are not so many in situ data available for model validation. Cruises only provide data sets which are irregular in space and time. Satellites observations only concern the sea surface, whereas ARGO, thanks to all its floats, will cover the top 2000 m of the world oceans. Once achieved, the ARGO data set might become a tool of importance for operational oceanography, as it gives systematic data from, often renewed, with a high spatial density, and carefully checked. Indeed, each measurement is given a “quality check” number, which makes it possible to select only trustful data.

TOPAZ is currently using the GDEM climatology as a validation tool. But this partly indicates how the model is drifting, since this climatology was used to initialize the model. In addition, this climatology only gives indications on the rough structures of the ocean, but no detail. It is not helpful to check if seasonal phenomenons are well described by a model.

To achieve validation of TOPAZ model, I had during the second part of my work in the Mohn Sverdrup Center to compute differences between TOPAZ forecasts and ARGO data, and find a clear way to display the results.

2.c Proceeding with ARGO data

There are Argo data from different profilers available on the Coriolis ftp server. Every week files containing data checked over the previous week and collected during the last month are released on the Internet.

First, looking at these data is helpful to understand how to use them, to see at which depths measurements are made, and how frequent they are. But this depends on the profiler, it can be every meter or every 10 meters or less. It is also irregular. There are usually more measurements in the upper layer, and less in the deepest part where salinity and temperature do not change much. There are also profilers which measure pressure, some other depths, and for others both pressure and depths are available. And not all profilers measure both salinity and temperature. Taking all this into account makes it possible to start the work with these data. The aim was to display differences between model and data.

Argo Float Deployment Plan : Atlantic Ocean (Last Update : 17-Mar-2005)

Fig 19: Map of ARGO float deployment in the Atlantic Ocean (updated in March 17th 2005). Not all these floats are currently active.

TOPAZ is a forecast model for the Atlantic. Therefore, only data from the Atlantic have to be considered (See Fig 19). This was the purpose of a first matlab routine: selecting from the relevant files all the profiles taken on a given day inside the Atlantic. Then, depths, temperature and salinity data were extracted from the NetCDF files and stored in ASCII files. Once computed, differences (data-model) for both temperature and salinity for each depth value were added to these files. This is used to plot model predictions vs data (see fig 20, 21 and 22).

On the profiles below (Fig 20, 21 and 22), model outputs are plotted both with and without using the interpolation scheme, showing that the interpolated profiles fit really well with what the model computed. Besides the salinity and temperature profiles, a map indicates the profile location.

Fig 20: Profile Comparison (1)

Fig 21: Profile Comparison (2)

I first proceed without taking into account the “quality check” criteria, and as a result had really strange profiles for the data (See Fig 22). But in other cases, there are almost no difference between model and data (See fig 21), which is good result for the model.

Fig 22: Instrument failure, for Salinity at least

Fig 22 shows the importance of the quality check operated, and the importance of getting rid of unrealistic values. Indeed, statistics computed with these wrong data have no meaning, and there is no possible interpretation. Whereas taking into account only the “good” data ensures relevant and trustful statistics.

When working with an ocean forecast model, statistics can be computed depending on several parameters:

location: Are all predictions accurate in a given area

period, seasonal results: Are the predictions good for a specific day, week or month

forecast time: Are the forecasts given 10 or 5 days in advance much better than the ones made 1 day in advance

The method chosen was to divide the Atlantic into square boxes, all with the same length which can be chosen by the user (for example 20°x20°). This size will mainly depend on the number of in situ data available. It will decrease with an increasing number of data. Differences between model and measurements made in each of these square areas are then averaged.

There are again several ways for computing a mean of differences for an area where several profiles of data are available. Indeed, not all the profiles have the same number of measurements. For some of them there are measurements every meter, while for some other it is only every 20 m or even less. And some profiles are from shallow areas, others go deeper. Finally, due to some instruments failures, some data have to be ignored, and it happens that for some profiles there is only one relevant measurement.

It is first possible to average differences along one profile, and then gather all the profiles belonging to the same box, and average again. This means that each profile has the same statistical weight, whatever the number of its measurements.

A second choice is to give any measurement the same statistical weight. The problem is that if there is one profile for which measurements are made every meter, this single profile might unbalance the statistics for the box it belongs to.

There is no known best way to proceed. However, it was decided to operate a thinning, which

means that the measurements of each profile were averaged so that not more than one value every 10m remains for the upper layer (above 50m), and not more than one value every 50m below 50m deep. It is these values, computed for all the profiles in the same box, which are averaged to give a mean difference value for that box. It was also decided to divide the water column into 3 layers: The first one above 50 m deep, the second between 50 m and 600 m deep, and the last one below 600 m (measurements are made down to 2000 m deep).

The results had to be clearly presented, so they can be shown on the TOPAZ website, on the validation pages. Besides the plots presented on fig 20, 21 and 22, the results of the statistics computation are displayed, also with matlab (See Fig 24, 25 and 26). One panel is made for each square box previously described. It is divided in two ranks, the upper one for Salinity and the lower one for Temperature. On such a panel, a map of the square box is drawn, with dots indicating profiles location. Besides this map, two histograms are made. One for the mean of differences, and one for the standard deviation. For each variable, 3 different mean or standard deviation values are displayed, one is for the first layer which is above 50m, one is for the second layer, between 50m and 600m, and the last one is for below 600m. The number of measurements for each layer is indicated.

The dots are plotted with a scale color indicating how many measurements were made for each profile. If the dot is green, it means that the profile contains less than 5 measurements, it is cyan if there are between 5 and 10 measurements, magenta if there are between 10 and 15, and red for more than 15. This is helpful for understanding the statistics. For example, if on a specific area there are green dots along the coasts, and red dots far from any coast line, it means that in a statistical point of view, the profiles in the open sea are much more important.

Seventeen mean values with the associated standard deviation are computed each month, corresponding to all the different forecasts or hindcasts time (from -6 days -analysis- to +10 days -forecast-). All data taken in one month are gathered, and compared to relevant model outputs. The resulting plots are shown on the TOPAZ validation webpage (<http://topaz.neresc.no/Class4/>). All the individual profiles (such as on Fig 20, 21 and 22) are also available on that webpage, as well as the ASCII files. The values above 9000 in these ASCII files are filled values which replace unrealistic data or lack of data (some profilers take only salinity or only temperature measurements).

Here are some of the results for June 2005, the ones available on the website at the time I am finishing my project. It is not that easy to make comparisons between different forecasts time, because in spite of the monthly average, the floats are moving from one day to another and the comparisons do not refer to the same points. It is not such a problem when there are a lot of floats in the same area, but it can be when there are less than 3 floats drifting in a square box (see Fig 24 a,b,c and d).

a) 1 day forecast

b) 2 days forecast

c) 3 days forecast

d) 4 days forecast

Fig 24: longitude from 20W to 0, latitude from 30S to 50S. On the 2 days and 3 days forecast (Fig b and c) some floats drifting southward appear in the area, providing more data than on the 1 day forecast (Fig a). Again, on the 4 days forecast, there is only one float left in the area. Fig a) and d) are comparable since the float is, in these 2 figures, at the same location. The results are really close to each other, maybe slightly better for the 1 day forecast. In this open sea area, the situation may be stable, with no short scale phenomenon, and neither the model prediction, nor the data change much with time. But notice the negative differences on Fig 24b)

For further illustration, the salinity results for the area between -80W and -60W and between 50N and 30N are now presented. It corresponds to North America/Canada, from north of Florida (Florida not included) up to the Gulf of St. Lawrence. A lot of floats are already launched there, but it is not where the model is giving the best results, because of the large amount of river outflows. The only floats which remains at the same location in all figures are those along the coast, where there is fresh water. There are many of these floats, but less than 5 measurements for each, because the area they are in is likely to be shallow. Therefore, we can assume that the coastal floats do not influence the results

for the deepest layer, and probably not the middle one. We notice that the mean of differences in salinity has a large negative value for the upper layer, surely due to these floats close to the coast. The difference is not so large in the mid layer. It is even positive for the deepest layer, with a usually low standard deviation, showing that the coastal floats actually do not give contribution to that deepest layer.

Not all the figures are shown here (Fig 25).

Fig 25 a) hindcast -6 days

Fig 25 b) hindcast -4 days

Fig 25 c) hindcast -2 days

Fig 25 d) nowcast

Fig 25 e) 2 days forecast

Fig 25 f) 4 days forecast

Fig 25 g) 6 days forecast

Fig 25 h) 8 days forecast

Fig 25 i) 10 days forecast

Here is a figure (Fig 26) of comparisons between model and data for all the 6 days forecast for June 2005, showing that the model is accurate in some areas. It is eastern of the Caribbean Sea.

Fig 26: 6 days forecast for 60W to 40W and 10N to 30N

And here is a profile related to the previous figure.

Fig 27: Comparison between a 6 days forecast and data at 25.49N and -50.72W

It would be interesting to compare these results to other models. Unfortunately, the same kind of statistics which used to be freely available on the HYCOM (American model) website, are not anymore. MERCATOR is also using ARGO dataset as a validation tool. Differences between model and data are computed as well, but in a really different way. The water column is divided in 5 layers which are 0m-50m, 50m-200m, 200m-700m, 700m-2000m and below 2000m (the comparisons for this last layer must come from other data). For each of these layers, a map is displayed with colored dots indicating data location. The color of these dots depends on the (model-data) difference. There are also dots for different terms “lead days” on the same map. In fact, the MERCATOR method is to take all the data collected on a given week and compare them with different terms. Even though the same data are used by TOPAZ and MERCATOR for their validation, there is no possible comparison between the results, because they are of a really different kind.

But it wasn't much work to adapt one routine to make the same maps as MERCATOR does, simply to make comparisons possible. The water column is divided into 4 layers, as well as in MERCATOR (the lowest one, below 2000m is missing with the data used). No thinning of the data is done here, we can assume that the data are regularly taken for each profile, or at least taken at relevant depths. To make the comparisons more friendly, it is now an averaged (model-data) difference which is displayed. It is the opposite as what was done previously, but it is what MERCATOR does. There are in these maps less dots than on MERCATOR maps, since MERCATOR is using other data than ARGO, and is also probably using data from mooring floats, which are time series. It is possible that in a close future, more data will be used for TOPAZ validation. The scale color is the same for both model, from -3C to +3C for temperature and -0.5 to 0.5 psu for salinity. It is not possible to see when differences are larger than these values, but it is better than not having a larger scale, and not seeing differences between 0.5 or 1 C difference.

Mercator includes the Mediterranean Sea, whereas TOPAZ forecasts the South Atlantic. So the areas shown are not exactly the same on the maps below. It is not for sure that they exactly cover the same period. The ones of MERCATOR are from their website, and it corresponds to the period 15th of June-29th of June 2005. (http://www.mercator-ocean.fr/html/produits/description/welcome_fr.html) The maps for TOPAZ are made with data collected between the 15th and the 22nd, compared with relevant forecasts.

Fig 28 a) Salinity, from 0m to 50m, MERCATOR

Fig 28 b) Salinity, from 0m to 50m, TOPAZ

Fig 29 a) Salinity, from 50m to 200m, MERCATOR

Fig 29 b) Salinity, from 50m to 200m, TOPAZ

Fig 30 a) Salinity, from 200m to 700m, MERCATOR

Fig 30 b) Salinity, from 200m to 700m, TOPAZ

Fig 31 a) Salinity, from 700m to 2000m, MERCATOR

Fig 31 b) Salinity, from 700m to 2000m, TOPAZ

The data used by both models are not exactly the same. In the future there might be agreements so that comparisons between data and models are made in the same way. This would help for drawing conclusions and improving global ocean forecasting.

However, we can notice that for the upper layer in the Labrador Sea, Norwegian Sea and around Iceland, the water in MERCATOR seems to be not salty enough, whereas it is too salty in TOPAZ. It is no longer the case below 700m, where in both models the water might be too salty, but this single example does not allow general conclusions.

On TOPAZ model, close to the southern boundary of the model the water is too salty, whereas it is generally not salty enough between about -25°S and 50°CN . We can notice that the maps for the 3rd (from 200m and 700m) and the 4th layer (from 700m and 2000m) are different, whereas for the computation of mean differences and standard deviation these two layers are gathered. Indeed, water is generally too fresh for the 3rd layer, almost everywhere, but it became too salty below the equator in the 4th layer.

Fig 32 a) Temperature, from 0m to 50m, MERCATOR

Fig 32 b) Temperature, from 0m to 50m, TOPAZ

Fig 33 a) Temperature, from 50m to 200m, MERCATOR

Fig 35 a) Temperature, from 700m to 2000m, MERCATOR

Fig 35 b) Temperature, from 700m to 2000m, TOPAZ

As a general observation, the water in NERSC seems to be too warm from 50m to 200m, whereas in MERCATOR it seems to be colder. Again, it is difficult to deduce generality from a single example.

On the first layer (Fig 33b), the differences between data and TOPAZ are sometimes positive, sometimes negative, without any large trend. It is not the case for the other layers, where there are no atmospheric and turbulent impacts. We notice the warm water close to the southern boundary.

In this part of the work I discovered the ARGO project, which should become a main tool in operational oceanography in the next few years. Working with these data was of interest since it made me see how they can be used and I had to deal with plenty of salinity and temperature profiles from all the Atlantic Ocean.

Conclusion

The comparisons between in one hand TOPAZ and MERCATOR and in the other hand TOPAZ and ARGO data is not completed yet. There are more conclusions to be drawn, and the work presented here hopefully provides tools for further work.

The Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center was a really nice and interesting place to work in. People are pleased to give any help when needed. It is also an international area inside Norway. During this work I mostly learned how to use matlab and make a routine work the right way. I also get more used to Linux environment.

I appreciated working with oceanography as a background, and my interest for studying oceanography increased during my year in Bergen. I hope I will have the opportunity to improve my knowledge and work again in that field.

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Comparison between MERCATOR and NERSC model forecasts for August the 18th 2004

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This report focuses on the one-week forecasts predicted by NERSC and MERCATOR (MERC) for August 18th 2004 in the Gulf of Mexico (GOM). This date has been chosen because it corresponds to the prior week to the eddy shedding event of the last summer.

First we analyzed tool efficiency for the front description, and compared the models result with the most accurate one. Then we compared the circulation by examining the respective cross section.

1 Front Comparison

Several parameters such as SSH, temperature and velocity gradient will be used to find the best description of the Loop Current (LC) and Loop Current Eddy (LCE) front.

1.a Temperature

Plotting isotherms at 200 meter depth shows where the front is located according to these two models. The depth 200m was chosen because it is deep enough to avoid seeing mesoscale features of the mixed layer. Such isotherms are shown on Fig 1 and Fig 2.

Fig 1. MERC, Isotherms at 200m depth, from 17 to 21°C

Fig 2. NERSC, Isotherms at 200m depth from 20 to 23°C

The best isotherm description of the front seems to be at 18°C for MERC and 21°C for NERSC.

1.b Other criteria

The velocity gradient is obviously the best criteria for the velocity front, which is of interest. But it is a very difficult variable to handle because it is noisy and not uniform. The velocity gradient method was applied to determine the accuracy of the SSH and isotherm criteria for representing the fronts.

Fig 3. MERCATOR inter-variable front comparison

Background: velocity gradient at the surface.

Isolines:

SSH 24 cm in green;

18°C isotherm at 200m depth in black

Fig 4. NERSC inter-variable front comparison

Background: velocity gradient at the surface.

Isolines: SSH 24cm in green; 20°C isotherm at 200m depth in black

The 200m depth isotherm method is more relevant since it fits slightly better the velocity gradient.

1. Inter-model front comparison

Fig 5. Background CLS

Black line: MERCATOR, isotherm 18°C, 200m deep

Blue line: NERSC, isotherm 21°C, 200m deep

From Fig 5 we can see that both models failed to describe accurately the northern front, but the NERSC model is (a bit) better.

For forecasting the eddy shedding, the NERSC model is too early, but MERC model seems too late (LC very broad).

This will be discussed later in the next chapter.
The orientation of the LC is better described in NERSC model.

2. Cross-section

Cross sections can be used to examine the model description of the basin hydrology, but also to see the depth of LC and LCE

2.a Temperature:

Fig 6. MERC: temperature section plot at 25°N

Minimum: 6,03°C

Maximum: 30,19°C

Fig 7. NERSC: temperature section plot at 25°N.

Minimum: 5,11°C

Maximum: 30,95°C

According to NERSC prediction, the eddy is deeper and some structures appear to the west of the LC due to a small eddy at 92°W (see Fig001). Cherubin et al. (2005, [6]) have shown that a deepening of the LC deepest active layer occurs before an eddy shedding event and is connected with growth of the neighboring cyclones.

That mechanism is clearly represented in the NERSC model (Fig 7), with a strong signal of 2 cyclonic eddies on each side of the LC (as in Fig 9) with maximal instability.

One cyclonic eddy is present also in the MERC model (Fig 6) but the shear is less pronounced.

Considering that we are in summer time we assume that both models suit the GDEM climatology (Fig 8).

Fig 8. Temperature, section 25°N, -100°W to -80°W and above 700m deep from GDEM Data
Minimum: 5,54°C,
Maximum: 29,56°C

Fig 9. Isotherm configuration along a vertical section across the deeply penetrating cyclonic feature on the boundary of the LC, for the 27 March 1979 from [1]

2.b Salinity

Fig 10. MERCATOR: salinity at 25°N
Minimum: 34,95 psu
Maximum: 36,46 psu

Fig 11. NERSC: salinity at 25°N
Minimum: 34,98 psu
Maximum: 36,34 psu

From Fig 11, one can see that the water in NERSC is too fresh near the surface and Gulf common water goes too deep (until 600 m); this is also evident in the MERC model (Fig 10) but MERC model is nearer to climatology.

None of the models manage to represent the typical subtropical underwater (SUW, 36.6 psu, 22.5°C) present in the near surface layer of the LC.

This can be due to insufficient inflow from the Caribbean Sea through the Yucatan Strait, or to a secondary impact of the assimilation.

From salinity and temperature section plot, we can see clearly that both models are too diffusive in the vertical dimension.

This phenomenon has been discussed in Barnier et al. (2001, [3])

Fig 12. Salinity, section 25°N, -100°W to -80°W and above 700m deep from GDEM Data
Minimum: 34,86 *Maximum: 36,53*

Northward Velocity

Fig 13. MERC northward velocity section at 25°N
Minimum: -0,71 m/s
Maximum: 1,07 m/s

Fig 14. NERSC northward velocity section at 25°N
Minimum value: -1,26 m/s
Maximum value: 1,33 m/s

Fig 15. Northward velocity from the model set up by [2].

The velocity is higher in the NERSC model, and we can clearly see the cyclonic eddy, which confirms the previous hypothesis.

3 Yucatan section

Recent studies such as [4] and [5] have shown the importance of the Yucatan inflow for the GOM circulation. We will study the section at 22°N.

3.a Temperature

Fig 16. MERCATOR, temperature
Minimum: 4,09°C
Maximum: 30,21°C

Fig 17. NERSC, temperature section
Minimum: 3,66°C
Maximum: 29,33°C

Considering that we are in summer, both models describe well the temperatures measurement. The tilt in the thermocline is better represented by the NERSC model.

Fig 18. Section across the Loop Current just north of the Yucatan Channel, based on data acquired on Cruise 62-H3. Plot extracted from [1]

3.b Salinity

Fig 19. MERCATOR, salinity section
Minimum: 34,95 psu
Maximum: 36,47 psu

Fig 20. NERSC, salinity section
Minimum value: 34,98 psu
Maximum value: 36,38 psu

In Fig 19 and Fig 20, except for the description of the SUW, which is too low, the comparison with Fig 22 is extremely good. The NERSC model represents better the tilt in the isohaline. Both models represent accurately the Antarctic intermediate deep water and the North Atlantic deep water.

The comparison between Fig 20 and Fig 21 reveals that the vertical interpolation of the model onto a standard grid does not allow a detailed interpretation of the sections. Many features are lost in the interpolation. However the vertical interpolation does not introduce biases and respects the vertical position of water masses and the slope of the density lines.

Fig 21. Original salinity section in the Yucatan Strait without vertical interpolation to standard levels. Isopycnals are shown as black lines.

Fig 22. Section across the Loop Current just north of the Yucatan Channel, based on data acquired on Cruise 62-H3. Data extracted from [1]

3.c Northward Velocity

Fig 23. MERC, northward velocity
 Minimum: -0,44 m/s
 Maximum: 1,44 m/s

Fig 24. NERSC, northward velocity
 Minimum: -0,44 m/s
 Maximum: 1,17 m/s

The inflow and outflow through the Yucatan Straits differ from one model to the other. The fastest outflow is close to the surface and on the eastern part of the section with MERC (Fig 23), whereas it extends more to the east with NERSC (Fig 24). For the inflow, MERC has higher velocities within a smaller area near the surface in the western part of the section (behaving like a intense coastal jet). What remains to be seen is whether the two models have the same salinity and temperature exchange through the Yucatan or not.

These two figures can be related to [2]. When the Loop Current front is growing northward, the upper inflow in the Yucatan strait is closer to the west coast and reaches a depth of 200m together with a maximum speed of 1,20 m/s. At the same time, a southward current flows on the eastern part of the Yucatan strait, to a depth of 400 m deep and with a lower speed of 0,25 m/s. This situation is the one simulated by MERC in Fig 24, and indeed, the eddy according to MERC forecast is still attached (Fig 1 and Fig 2). Then, according to [2], when the eddy has reached its highest latitude, and has been separated, the current in the Yucatan strait can slow down to 0,40 m/s, and spread eastward, remaining at the same depth. The southward outflow is also slower, it moves eastward and remains at 800m depth. This is more or less the description of the NERSC simulation, while in Fig 21, the forecast of the NERSC model, the eddy is no longer attached (see Fig 1 and Fig 2).

Fig 25: Section across the Yucatan Strait representing an estimate of the geostrophic velocity component normal to the section.

Red is for the northward flow (into the Gulf), Green is for the southward flow (into the Caribbean)

Last updated 21 December 2003. [1]

Conclusion:

About front detection we have seen that 200m isotherm is more accurate than SSH isoline. Using that we showed that on the 18th of August, both models have the Northern LC front too far south. NERSC model eddy has shed too early, while MERCATOR LC is still in growing phase without instability.

So NERSC model has overall better dynamical state, while MERCATOR has better water mass properties.

This comparison is valid for nowcast on the 18th of August and should be repeated before we can conclude on the model predictive skills.

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Model Vertical interpolation

The model results imply some treatments to compare them to measurements taken at several depths. Indeed, the model uses density layers through the water column: the depth and the size of each layer are not fixed in time.

Moreover, the velocity given by the model is the one in the middle of the layer. It is defined as a vertical average over the layer. Thus the vertical velocity distribution is a discrete one.

The actual vertical interpolation used is a second order spline with specific conditions for the first layer and the bottom.

The constraints applied on the second order polynomial are:

- Continuity of the spline function at layer interfaces.
- Continuity of the derivative of the spline function at layer interfaces.
- Conservation of mean velocity within each layer.

In the upper layer, the treatment is slightly different. The upper half of the layer is assumed to have a constant velocity. In the lower half we fit a polynomial. At the sea bed the lower layer velocity is specified.

This method presents some problems when the stratification is too strong at the top of the water column.

Considering Fugro's report, several interpolations methods have been tested: kriging, higher order splines, linear interpolation.

In order to conserve the physical properties of the model in each layer, two principal characteristics of the vertical interpolation are taken into account:

- Continuity of the spline function at layer interfaces.
- Conservation of mean velocity within each layer.

The continuity avoids discontinuities in time series at fixed depth when the layer boundary is crossed.

The slab function is not considered because of its discontinuity, which can mess up harmonic analyses for example.

The linear interpolation tested, respects the constraints of continuity and the conservation of the mean over each layer. The first layer considered is assumed to have a constant velocity. But, this method gives a deviation too strong to be considered (Figure 1).

Higher order splines and kriging were also found inappropriate.

Thus, we finally focused on the present method with some modifications on the first and the last layer where we sat up a linear polynomial, which respects the constraints of continuity and the conservation of the mean velocity.

1. Tests on Fugro's example

Current profiles from Fugro's example are illustrated in Figure 1 by using the slab function, linear interpolation, 'old' and 'new' spline from the top to the bottom of the water column.

This shows principally how strong is the deviation from the linear interpolation, when it is constrained to respect layer averages.

Concerning the 'new' spline's result, it is better than the older one on the first layer but the variation of the velocity between the first and the second layer seems to be too strong to be controlled by the spline.

Figure 1 Current profiles derived from different interpolations methods

Consequently, we decided to use the 'new' spline method only from the second layer to the bottom of the water column by assuming that the velocity on the first layer is constant. Current profiles derived from the data, the slab function, the 'old' spline and the 'new' one are compared on the Figure 2 and Figure 3.

This compromise implies discontinuity between the first and the second layer but on the other hand it gives encouraging results along the profile (Figures 2, 3)

To get the larger view of the behavior of the spline along the water column, it has been tested on a long time series.

Figure 2 Current Profiles derived from different interpolations

Figure 3: Zoom on the first 100 meters of the vertical interpolation of the Figure 2

2. Analyze on a typical model time series

We used the hindcast data set of the Gulf of Mexico model from the 21st of September to the 29th of November 2004. There was no hurricane during that period.

The station location is 90.14 W, 27.283 N.

We have chosen this specific area because of the wild range of situations that can happen there.

This location is successively in a warm eddy, at the boundary between this eddy and a cyclonic and finally into the cyclonic eddy.

The figure 4 shows the shape of the profiles that we obtain in this area.

Figure 4: Trend of the first profile of the time series used for the QQ-plots

Since there is no corresponding observation, we are comparing different model results by looking at quantile-quantile plots of:

- The hindcast results along the water column between the ‘new’ against the ‘old’ interpolation (first row of the figures 5, 6 and 7)
- And the hindcast results between the ‘new’ interpolation against the slab function (the second row of the figures 5, 6 and 7)

The non-exceedence percentiles included are from 2% to 100% with a step of 2%.

The results from the first comparison, on the first row of the figures 5, 6, 7, show that the modifications applied on the spline function does not influence so much the general shape of the interpolation.

On the other hand, the plots derived from the slab function and the ‘new’ spline interpolation suggest that the interpolation is really close from the speed given by the model at the exception of the extreme values for the first 100 meters.

From 150 meters to 350 meters, the ‘new’ spline follows the trend of the slab function for medium values but then it tends to overestimate speeds of very high non-exceedence percentiles at 150 meters, then successively overestimates and underestimates them at 200 meters and slightly underestimates them at 350 meters. This corresponds to speeds at the bottom of the eddy, and one or several density interfaces. However, no systematic bias is observed on this test database. In deeper water, the qq-plots are given in a smaller range of speed. It shows clearly that the spline does not deviate much from the slab function, but still behaves irregularly at some points.

This confirms that the deviation of the interpolation with the model output for each layer is reasonably small.

Concerning the seabed properties, it is now assumed to be linear with the conservation of the mean velocity of the layer. The bottom exerts a frictional stress against the flow, bringing the velocity gradually to zero within a thin layer above the bottom. This is not taken into account but in the future, we are planning some developments, including the bottom boundary layer in the model.

We therefore suggest:

- A change of closure conditions at the top and the bottom (linear instead of quadratic).
- To replace the ‘old’ spline with the ‘new’ spline (with a slab for the first layer).

Figure 5: Quantile plots of Hindcast current speed at depths 13, 30, 55 and 100 meters, 'new' vs. 'old' spline and slab function.

Figure 6: Quantile Quantile plots of the Hindcast current speed at the depths 150, 200 and 350 meters, ‘new’ spline vs. ‘old’ spline and slab function.

Figure 7: Quantile plots of Hindcast current speed at depths 750, 950, 1200, 1430 meters, ‘new’vs ‘old’ spline and slab function.

